

WOMEN'S COURAGE BEHIND THE FRONT DURING THE YEARS OF WORLD WAR II. (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE KASHKADARYA REGION)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359044>

Annotation: this article Details women who worked behind the front during the years of World War II. The work of women in the field of Agriculture, in leadership positions, the courage shown by them is illuminated.

Keywords: World War II, Nazi Germany, Soviet Union, oblast, ruble, collective farm, evacuation, "Red Uzbekistan", "Red soldier", "movement", "Vostok", "October 15th anniversary".

It is known that during the years of the Second World War, the will of the women of Uzbekistan passed a huge test of their perseverance. That is, the patriotic qualities inherent in the nature of Uzbek women became more pronounced during the war years.

According to archival documents, in the early days of the war, more than 14 thousand petitions from volunteers fell on the military commissariats of the city and District of the Republic, among which 6 thousand were made up of women. On the second hand, they worked selflessly inside the country, contributing to the victory. The thousands of women who stayed behind the Front shouted "everything is for the front!", "To the protection of motherland!", "Behind the Front as on the front!", "Only forward and forward!", "Don't go home without completing the assignment!", "Who worked well today should work even better tomorrow", mobilized to the Labor Front under the slogans "who worked for himself today should work for two tomorrow".[1: 141] during this period, women were the main factor in securing the place of the male workforce that went to the front.

The years of World War II also saw great difficulties in the agricultural sector. Farmers working in agriculture were faced with a front and the task of providing the population of the interior of the country with agricultural products, and industry with raw materials. In the September 12, 1941 issue of the newspapers" Pravda Vostoka "and" Red Uzbekistan", the murajaat of the peasants of the Yangiyul District of the Tashkent region was announced. In this appeal, all agricultural workers were urged to work hard until the enemy was routed, to obtain a rich harvest of cotton, to show diligence in the supply of agricultural products necessary for the front and industry. As a result of the

widespread involvement of qualified specialists, able-bodied men in the front line, the defense industry, the number of men who were able to work in the collective farms of the Republic decreased by 32 percents. In such conditions, women formed the main force in agricultural production. During the period of cotton harvesting, nationwide competitions among women were in full swing. Women from the kashkadarya region, such as The Immortal Sadriyeva, Salomat Qarshiyeva, worked effectively and showed diligence in the harvesting of cotton.

The war also necessitated the development of silkmaking, an important branch of Uzbekistan's agriculture. In order to increase the production of silk products in the country, to train qualified silk specialists, the Central Committee of the CPC (b) decided on March 13, 1941 "on measures to further develop silk production in Uzbekistan". This decision outlined the specific tasks of increasing silk production in the Republic, increasing the yield of flax. According to these decisions, it was envisaged that in the next 6-7 years Uzbekistan sawmills would bring the harvesting of sawdust to 20 thousand tons, achieving the extraction of 50 kilograms of sawdust from each box of sawmills.

In 1942, Uzbek women of sawmills worked effectively. In this year, thanks to the selfless work of women, 12,190 tons of sawdust were prepared for the state. The state plan for the preparation of the saw was completed in 103.5 percents. In this process, counter district sawmills received an average of 58.7 from each box of saw seeds, and Lighthouse district sawmills received 51.1 kilograms. During the years of World War II, special attention was paid to the issue of grain cultivation in agriculture. One of the main grain-growing regions was considered the Kashkadarya region. During this period, T. of the collective farm Kuibyshev in the peasant District of the region. The Subanova Chief women's brigade performed well in the harvesting of grain. T.Subanova herself performed work from 3 norms per day. Members of the kolkhoz "Aktazkom" in Beshkent district Norkhol Shodiyeva, Zaynab Sharipova, Mastura Odilova and others worked from 3-3.5 norms at the time of grain harvest.[2: 72] for this reason, during the war years, gross grain production was brought to 104 million Poods. Also, the cultivation of sugar beets, necessary for the front and the inner regions of the country, was established. Samarkand, Fergana, Tashkent, Kashkadarya regions were specialized in the cultivation of beets, sugar beets were planted on fertile lands of 65 thousand hectares as early as 1942, and more than 70 thousand hectares in subsequent years.[3:152]

In October 1941, women of the Tashkent district were the first in Uzbekistan to take the initiative to voluntarily help the family of fighters at the

front. This initiative was also supported by other women in the Republic. Such actions were also carried out in the Kashkadarya region. Peasant farms such as "Alanga" of the yertepa Rural Council of Qarshi district, Yusupov, Okhunboboyev in the Mirmiron rural council, "Red soldier" in the Khudoyzot rural council, "movement", "Vostok", "October 15th anniversary" set an example in organizing assistance to the frontline families.[4: 82] members of the "Red soldier" "peasant farm made 2 centners of wheat, 5 centners of vegetables, 2 thousand rubles of money, 10 garams of firewood, members of the "target" peasant farm in the Kat village council made 40 garams of firewood. They collected and handed over 5,000. In particular, an exemplary organization was organized to organize assistance to families displaced as a result of temporary necessity from the front line. They were provided with housing, fuel. In the first and second MTS communities in Qarshi district, organizing aid to the families of the front workers became public. After the front-line family Krivyanina was provided with housing he was taught the profession of electropayvandlik, Lopacheva tokarlik, Choliyeva the profession of autogeny.

Since women were considered the main factor in ensuring the country's economic potential during the years of World War II, their labor was also used, mainly in leadership positions. In particular, in the pre-war period, a busy women's salute in the position of leader represented only 280 women in the Republic, 1.2% of the total leadership staff, while during the period 1944-1945, 940 women in party and Soviet organizations served in leadership positions. For this reason, courses were opened in all regions and districts of Uzbekistan preparing collective farms chairman, deputy chairman, Brigadier, accountant and other specialists in order to prepare personnel and management personnel for production.

In 1942, 1,400 women worked in the Kashkadarya Region farms in the positions of heads of cotton, grading zveno. In the provincial Chirochi District, 45 women were elected deputy chairman of farms and 72 women were elected chairman of the Pentecostal Council. In the kashkadarya region, 581 progressive women were made deputy chairmen and 207 women were made brigadiers. [5:34]

Thus, during the war years, women took the lead in all areas. It became a retaining link, providing support for victory in all respects. Women's Labor was used in all areas of industry, agriculture. In particular, the organizer, leading girls, stood in front in all areas and worked hard. Women's labour in leadership positions was also effective.

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